

Reactions of Stannic Isopropoxide with Trimethylacetoxysilane

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Search for polymeric materials has aroused the interest in the metal siloxides¹. Rochow and Tatlock² have prepared tetrakis (trimethylsiloxy) tin by the reaction between potassium silanolate and stannic chloride. Tetrakis (triphenylsiloxy) tin³ has been reported by analogous reaction with sodium triphenyl-silanolate.

As the simple reaction of stannic alkoxide with trimethyl-acetoxysilane does not appear to have been investigated, it was considered of interest to make its detailed study. It is tempting to mention a striking difference in behaviour of germanium⁴, the tetraiso-propoxide of which does not undergo any such reaction under similar condition. In view of the condensation tendency of trimethylacetoxysilane, its solution in cyclohexane was added dropwise to stannic isopropoxide, $\text{Sn}(\text{OPr}^i)_4$, Pr^iOH , refluxing in cyclohexane; the isopropyl acetate liberated in the reaction was simultaneously fractionated out azeotropically. After the reaction was over, the product was isolated by removing the solvent under reduced pressure. The stepwise reactions may be represented as follows:

The mono- and di-substituted derivatives.

$[(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{SiO Sn}]_2(\text{OPr}^i)_2$ and $[(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{SiO}]_2\text{Sn}(\text{OPr}^i)_2$ appeared to undergo decomposition when heated under reduced pressure. The monoisopropoxy tris (trimethylsiloxy) tin derivative suffers disproportionation when heated to yield tetrakis product which was found to be monomeric in boiling benzene.

1. Lappert and Leigh, 'Developments in Inorganic Polymer Chemistry', Elsevier Publishing, 1962.
2. Tatlock and Rochow, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1955, 77, 1555.
3. Gutman and Meller, *Monatsh Chem.*, 1960, 91, 579.
4. Chandra, Thesis, Rajasthan University, Jaipur, 1963.

EXPERIMENTAL

Apparatus and chemicals have already been described in one of the authors' previous publications⁵. Stannic isopropoxide was prepared as described⁶. Molecular weight was determined by semi-micro Callenkamp Ebulliometer.

TABLE I

Reaction of stannic isopropoxide with trimethylacetoxysilane

Reactants (g)	Molar ratio	Product (yield, g)	Analysis%				Action of heat under reduced pressure
			Found		Calculated		
Sn (OPr ⁱ) ₄	X Pr ⁱ OH (a)	(CH ₃) ₃ Si ⁻ OCF ₃ (b)	Sn	OPr ⁱ	Sn	OPr ⁱ	
(a) 3.85	1:1	Light pale viscous liquid	31.2	46.0	30.8	46.0	1.8g heated to 140° bath/0.2 mm. to yield a white sublimate having Sn, 36.2; OPr ⁱ 37.0%.
(b) 1.22		Sn (OPr ⁱ) ₃ [OSi (CH ₃) ₃] ₃ (3.5)					
(a) 4.2	1:2	Colourless waxy solid	29.4	28.5	28.6	28.4	Attempted sublimation (1.6 g) gave a white solid (0.8) at bath 180-200°/0.6-0.8 mm. having Sn, 32.6; OPr ⁱ , 19.0%.
(b) 2.68		Sn (OPr ⁱ) ₂ [OSi (CH ₃) ₃] ₄ (4.16)					
(a) 2.12	1:3	Viscous liquid	26.4	19.2	26.6	19.2	When the product (1.8) is heated, a white solid (1.05) is distilled at 78-80°/1.2 mm. Found: Sn, 25.0. Required for Sn [OSi (CH ₃) ₃] ₄ Sn, 24.9%.
(b) 2.02		Sn (OPr ⁱ) [OSi (CH ₃) ₃] ₃ (2.18)					
(a) 2.05	1:4	Low melting solid* distillable	24.8	—	24.9	—	at 74-76°/0.3mm. Sn[OSi(CH ₃) ₃] ₄ (1.8 g)
(b) 2.61							

*Found Mol. wt., 477; Required, 475.

For metal analysis, the weighed sample was taken in a platinum crucible and was moistened with ammonia. Removal of excess of ammonia was followed by the addition of few drops of hydrofluoric acid. The crucible was kept at 100-110°C for about three hours to remove silicon tetrafluoride and the residue was ignited to SnO₂.

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5. Mehrotra and Pant, *this Journal*, 1963, 4, 109.

6. Mehrotra and Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 43, 153.